

Conceptual framework for analyzing and designing bending-active tensile hybrid structures

Evy L. M. SLABBINCK*, Seiichi SUZUKI^a, Jonathan J. SOLLY^a, Anja MADER^a, Jan KNIPPERS^a

*Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design (itke), Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, University of Stuttgart, Germany, Keplerstrasse 11, 70174 Stuttgart-Germany, e.slabbinck@itke.uni-stuttgart.de

^a Institute for Building Structures and Structural Design (itke), Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, University of Stuttgart, Germany

Abstract

In this paper, the core elements of bending-active tensile (BAT) hybrid structures are defined and a classification system is proposed based on the relationship between the active and passive use of the structural elements. Form, efficiency and the future development potential of various hybrid systems is investigated. Only a handful BAT have been built the last decade, and for every structure and system a new combination of words is proposed. This work aims to provide a general-purpose dictionary of considered terminology that can be utilized by researchers in this expanding field to ensure clear description of new findings.

BAT hybrid structures are a recently-developed structural typology characterized by the use of reciprocal equilibrium between bending-active and tensile elements of the primary load-bearing system. Though these structures have a high degree of structural efficiency (Lienhard and Knippers [20]), only a few experimental and research-oriented structures have been built. These have been limited in scale and functionality due to the complexity in design, simulation and analysis, fabrication and construction.

The work presented is intended as an aid to understanding different types of BAT hybrid structures. This is achieved through the analysis and comparison of recently-built BAT hybrid demonstrator structures. Strategies for the digital modelling and simulation of these complex structures are also discussed. A tight integration between design and analysis is required for BAT hybrid structures due to form, internal stresses and global stability being entirely interdependent. In the case of most bending-active structures this interconnected design/simulation is particularly complex due to the large deformations experienced by the system during the process of finding a stable equilibrium condition, a scenario that many software packages cannot easily solve.

Keywords: Bending-active, hybrid structures, membrane structures, form-finding, structural system

1. Introduction

Tensile surface form-active structures have been built for decades and are still present in our daily lives (Engel [12]). If designed well, these are among the most efficient loadbearing systems as the internal forces are mainly in pure axial tension so buckling problems are not raised (Knippers *et al.* [15]). These lightweight and freeform structures are often used for large span applications using minimum material. The design of these membranes requires a form optimization process as the exact form cannot be predicted through simple geometric description and must be form-found to ensure a self-stressed equilibrium. Traditionally, these structures are supported by struts, cables and trusses to be able to transfer the high reaction forces of the pre-stressed membrane to bending stiff supports. In bending-active tensile (BAT) structures these forces can be resolved internally.

The BAT typology is relatively new and is based on the use of bending-active elements, or splines (Adriaenssens [2]), as a support system. These are slender elements that are initially straight and are then bent in an elastic way (Knippers *et al.* [15]). In the BAT typology these are then combined with tensile elements, i.e. membranes or cables. The coupling of these form-active and section-active elements may create a reciprocal equilibrium that can be designed as a self-tensioning/supporting system and reduces the thrust onto the supports. Other advantages of these structures lie in both structural systems and their reciprocal equilibrium, i.e. bending-active elements and membranes can be fabricated and transported in a compact flat packed configuration. The reciprocal equilibrium seen in BAT structures can be compared to the well-known bow. The initially-straight bow is braced and kept in a bent state by a string. At the moment when the bow is drawn, additional energy is stored in the elastically-deformed bow. When the arrow is released the string transfers part of this elastic potential energy into kinetic energy in the arrow, which enables a greater speed possible than any human throw would be capable of. (Kooi *et al.* [16]) (Beukers [7]) This concept of storing energy can be translated from 1D structural elements to a 3D form that uses a tensile surface and bending-active elements, called a bending-active tensile hybrid (BATH) structure. On the one hand the membranes keep the bending-active element bent and make sure they don't buckle, on the other hand the bending-active elements create the doubly-curved geometry of the membrane and provide it with the pre-stress required.

This system hybridity is discussed later in this paper and defined within both traditional and BAT (hybrid) structures. A differentiation in types of BATH structures is also suggested based on the relationship between form and efficiency. Advantages and future potentials will be highlighted and weak spots indicated.

2. BATH structures

2.1 History and definition

Only a handful BAT structures have been built the last decade, and for every structure and system a new combination of words is proposed, leaving the term 'hybrid' in these structural systems undefined. Previous research (Lienhard *et al.* [22]) indicates that the first hybrid structure constructed of elastic beams integrated in a form-active surface is found in the work done on 'Stressed Spline Structures' that was motivated by the Oleada concept introduced at the Expo in Seville in 1992 (Adriaenssens [1]). In this project the membrane was shaped by tensegrity arches. Other relevant precedent work is found in the research pavilion using bending-active GFRP arches combined with a prestressed membrane built by ITKE in 2004 (Knippers *et al.* [15]). To determine the first true bending-active tensile hybrid structure ever built, one has to create a clear definition for these structures and see if the options meet these criteria. By looking at several demonstrators by other researchers tackling hybridity, an attempt is being made to define a complete definition that describes BATH structures.

The word 'hybrid' is defined as the combination of two different elements (Oxford dictionary [28]), and is often used in building construction and architecture, e.g. 'hybrid construction' uses different material in different components (Vambersky [34]), 'hybrid buildings' may have two or more lateral load-resisting systems for seismic loading conditions (Vineetha *et al.* [36]), 'hybrid membrane structures' use a flexible membrane fabric within a rigid steel structure (Gioncu [13]), etc.

BAT structures could be considered as synergetic through the following definition introduced by Luchsinger and Crettol in 2007 [24]: "Synergetic structures are comprised of at least two components with different properties which complement each other to a new entity by means of constructive interactions". This definition defines synergy between different structural elements, in the case of BATH structures this would be section-active and form-active elements (Knippers *et al.* [15]), and

points out that they must interact in a beneficial way. However, this statement is incomplete and too general to describe the full detail BAT hybrid structures. As far as the complex structural interaction is concerned, it is usually difficult to define it completely. Nevertheless, an initial definition can be proposed based on Lienhard *et al.* [21] describing ‘textile hybrid’ in 2012 as: “*The use of elastically bent (bending-active) beam elements, as an intricate support system integrated with membrane surfaces, offers a great potential for new shapes and highly efficient structural systems for mechanically pre-stressed membranes. Such an integrated structural logic is being termed a textile hybrid*”. With this general defined concept all structures that are constructed from bending-active beam elements and an integrated membrane surface without having a beneficial reciprocity can be related to the *textile hybrid* principle. The difficulties in establishing a complete and clear definition is not based on the wording but on the systems built as BATH systems. The following paragraph analyzes these structures so it is possible to extend this first proposed definition while maintaining a close relationship with the conceptual idea itself.

2.2 BATH Typology

The BATH projects that are considered in this discussion, with as boundary condition using a structural membrane and/or is built in an outdoor environment, are the BAT wing (Off [27]), Marrakech Umbrella (Lienhard and Knippers [20]), Textile Hybrid M1 (Ahlquist *et al.* [3]), Restrained arch (Alpermann and Gengnagel [4]), Bending-active canopy (De Laet *et al.* [11]), and Hybrid tower (Holden Deleuran *et al.* [14]). These built demonstrators have been described as ‘*hybrid bending-active constructions*’ (De Laet *et al.* [11]), ‘*textile hybrids*’ (Lienhard *et al.* [21]) (Ahlquist *et al.* [3]), ‘*hybrid structures*’ (Lienhard *et al.* [22]) (Alpermann and Gengnagel [4]), ‘*bending active tensile membrane hybrid structure*’ (Holden Deleuran *et al.* [14]) and ‘*form-active hybrid structures*’ (Quinn *et al.* [31]).

In the previous chapter the ‘*bow*’ principle was defined to illustrate the reciprocal equilibrium of both structural elements. Therefore, the important requirements for this system hybrid-principle are: (1) the membrane keeps the bending-active elements bent, (2) the membrane enhances the buckling strength of the bending-active elements, and (3) the bending-active elements make sure the membrane is doubly curved and prestressed.

Considering these requirements, similar aspects are found in Off in 2010 (Off [27]): “*it is a membrane with flexible reinforcement fiber rods, able to take compression forces under buckling state secured and anchored with the membrane surface itself*”, in Alpermann in 2013 (Alpermann and Gengnagel [5]): “*...couple the actively bent elements using a membrane. The membrane restraints the bent elements to one another*”, as well as in the paper of De Laet in 2013 (De Laet *et al.* [11]): “*combining elastically bent elements with a tension structure creates a hybrid bending-active construction. The interacting components can be connected in such a way that the system is self-tensioned and the action required to bend the spline elements into a curved shape is resolved internally*”. Lienhard in 2013 (Lienhard *et al.* [22]) at his turn defined it as: “*...rods that pre-stress the membrane by means of elastic bending*”, Philipp in 2013 (Philipp and Bletzinger [29]) stated that: “*...advantageously unite form-found membrane and elastically deformed members to a new type of structure*”. More recent statements were made by Brancart in 2014 (Brancart *et al.* [8]): “*...owe their structural performance to the combination of slender linear elements and a membrane. Connecting them creates a self-tensioning system in which the bent elements become geometrically restrained by the membrane that is in turn pretensioned by the bending resistance of the linear elements*”, by Holden Deleuran in 2015 (Holden Deleuran *et al.* [14]): “*...a form active structural system exploring the potential of combining bending and tensile members for architectural design*”, and as last Quinn in 2016 (Quinn *et al.* [31]): “*...a structure in which the internal forces are assigned to materials or components to which they are best suited ...tensile elements are supported at their edges by actively-bent slender rods*”. We can map these principles related to the discussed projects in an overview matrix (Figure 01).

Project	Name and reference project	Year	Amount BAE	Tensile part	(1) Does membrane bent BAE	(2)(3) Does BAE prestress + doubly curve the membrane
	BAT wing, Off [27]	2010	7 BAE	Structural fabric	Yes	Yes
	Marrakech umbrella, Lienhard and Knippers [20]	2011	6 BAE	Structural fabric	Yes	Yes
	Textile Hybrid M1, Ahlquist <i>et al.</i> [3]	2012	5 BAE	Structural fabric (Ferrari 402)	No	Yes
	Restrained arch, Alpermann and Gengnagel [4]	2012	1 BAE	Structural fabric + cables	No	No
	Bending-active canopy, De Laet <i>et al.</i> [11]	2013	2 BAE + 1 strut	Structural fabric + cables	No	No
	Hybrid tower, Holden Deleuran <i>et al.</i> [14]	2015-2017	> 10 BAE	Knitted fabric + cables	No	No

Figure 01: Overview matrix concerning data on built BAT structures (BAE: bending-active elements)

A first overview shows that only two of the previous projects would be validated to be a full bending-active tensile hybrid structure according to the defined principles. Therefore, we introduce and define a more specific categorization with the following terms: ‘Global BATH structures’, ‘Local BATH structures’ and ‘Bending-active tensile structures’.

2.2.1 Global BATH structures

Global BATH structures are truly hybrid in their reciprocal equilibrium by means that both structural elements are load bearing and beneficial for one another. A side note has to be made here that when talking about tensile elements, surface membranes are meant. The membrane restrains the bending-active elements and keep them in their bent position so that the internal stresses, stored in the elements by bending them in an elastic way, can be used for pre-stressing and forming a doubly-curved membrane geometry. Due to this reciprocal equilibrium and the high complexity within these structures, discussed in paragraph 4, there is only a small window for the static equilibrium and the equilibrium with external forces to work (Figure 02).

Figure 02: Examples of global BATH structures

2.2.2 Local BATH structures

Local BATH structures still have a reciprocal equilibrium between the bending-active elements and the membrane, and gain the advantages of this coupling, but the membrane doesn't keep the bending-active elements bent. The bending-active elements are coupled to themselves, other bending-active elements, rigid laterally-resistance supports or with supporting cables. This doesn't mean that the membrane becomes only cladding, the membrane deforms the initial equilibrium state of the bending elements and stabilizes the structure. Advantages of these local BATH structures is that the redundancy in the system is greater than in in the global BATH structures (Figure 03).

Figure 03: Examples of local BATH structures

2.2.3 BAT structures

BAT structures, or according to Gioncu [13] 'Hybrid membrane structures', use a membrane surface applied to a fixed bending-active typology so the reciprocal equilibrium described above doesn't exist. The membrane is prestressed by an external system not linked to the internal energy in the bending-active elements, i.e. cables, ground anchors, and so on (Figure 04).

Figure 04: Example of BAT structure

2.3 The principle of system hybridity

One can find these system hybrid principles of achieving interconnected equilibrium between self-unstable structural elements in other lightweight constructions, e.g. tensairity, tensegrity, grid shells with a membrane as third layer. The combination of the two load-bearing elements in these structural systems, i.e. pneumatic-cable, strut-cable, and bending elements – membrane, are also in a reciprocal beneficial equilibrium and don't have the same structural performance without one of the two elements. Next to the lightweight construction world, these hybrid principles can be found in traditional structures, where pretensioned cables are added to improve the buckling strength of the critical members next to the stabilizing effect, to increase the overall structural integrity. Wembley stadium is a good example where the cables are used to induce initial compressive stresses to counterbalance the analyzed design internal forces so that failure can be deferred (Belenya [6]) (Mann [25]) (Figure 05).

Figure 05: Principle of Wembley stadium – cables improve buckling strength of the arch

2.4 The first BATH structure

Returning to the initial question of what can be considered as the first BATH structure, is the well-known outdoor tent, and more specifically the development of the pop-up tents in the last decade. In an architectural research environment, the GFRP and membrane pavilion 2004 (Knippers *et al.* [15]) achieves all the defined requirements (Figure 06a), but Adriaenssens (Adriaenssens [1]) took a big step in the initial development of the BATH structures with her ‘Span Spliced Spline Stressed Membranes’ (Figure 06b).

Figure 06: (a) Membrane pavilion 2004 (Knippers *et al.* [15]) (b) Spline Stressed Membranes (Adriaenssens [1])

3. Structural concept discussion for BATH Systems

Concept criteria for BATH structures are numerous: mechanical and material requirements, geometry, etc. This chapter is an allocation for different concepts, its purpose is to aid the understanding of the role of the load bearing elements in defining the performance of the complete structure.

BATH systems have intrinsic characteristics related to their reciprocal equilibrium and reaction forces, a general division into two broad structural classes is made: (1) *Stable self-equilibrated* and (2) *stable self-stressed-equilibrated*. All BATH structural systems are defined as stable as the system has the ability to reestablish its equilibrium state after an impact of external loads, as long as this impact doesn't interfere with the elastic performance of the bending elements. The structure is self-equilibrated on the one hand when it's in static equilibrium, i.e. all forces are resolved through a form-finding process, e.g. Textile Hybrid M1 (Ahlquist *et al.* [3]). Typically, in these structures it is the fixed support condition of the bending-active elements that transfers the loads incurred through bending to the ground. On the other hand, in a self-stressed-equilibrated structure, also called self-tensioned (De Laet *et al.* [11]), the structure requires no external support to maintain its non-externally-loaded form and the internally-introduced stresses created through bending are handled by

this self-tensioning so that no reaction forces influence the environment, e.g. BAT wing (Off [27]). The structure is free-standing and in most cases only needs a pin-support for uplifting and lateral wind forces, and due to the lightweight concept the structure has an unpredefined spatial direction. Also here a process, i.e. form-finding process, is needed to find the equilibrated nodal coordinates and distribution of the self-stress (prestress) to achieve a global equilibrium of the system. Both systems have internal prestress when no external forces are applied, which gives rigidity to the system, and are defined as statically indeterminate structures.

In BATH systems the structural elements are very recognizable and the behavior of the complete system is not easily predictable by considering the behavior of any of the structural elements separately, due to their reciprocal equilibrium.

On the one hand there are the bending-active elements, which in most cases are rods (Off [27]) (Lienhard *et al.* [22]) (Quinn *et al.* [31]), discarding other cross-sections like plates, while these were very successfully used for many of years in projects like Multihalle Mannheim by Frei Otto (Krasko [18]) and the ICD/itke Research pavilion 2010 (Lienhard *et al.* [19]).

The bending-active elements can stay active after a static equilibrium state is reached to enable multiple-stages of equilibrium and allow adaptive or evolving overall geometry (first theoretical concept by Brancart *et al.* [8]), or they can become passive, i.e. fixed in place, and only change under external loading. The slender bending-active elements are still advantages for construction, fabrication and transportation. Next to these specific section-bending-active members, the use of struts or compression rings (for stressing conical shaped membranes) can also be integrated in the structure.

Other work goes into the topic of mechanical and material requirements, including the importance of creep in these structures, and is not further discussed in this paper (Lienhard *et al.* [22]) (Kotelnikova-Weiler *et al.* [17]).

4. Future potential and occurring problems

In 2011, Muttoni said that structures have a more important function than just being supports or resist loads. The purpose of the structure is to connect with its use and its architectural function (Muttoni [26]). With BATH, as spatial lightweight structure, there is a direct link between architectural function and structure, the structure is the space created.

Considering the many variables that come into play in the reciprocal behavior of BATH systems, their design and simulation is complex and difficult. The simplicity of the smooth geometry is not reflected in their simulation process as their behavior is non-linear, and requires a second order calculation and form-finding process. Consequently, the design of BATH systems is an iterative process. As pointed out by Correia de Melo (Correia de Melo *et al.* [9]) the object appears a priori in the designer's mind. However, with this reciprocal equilibrium, structural efficiency and complexity, and the necessity for a form-finding process, the designer has no intuitive design strategy. Traditionally, structures are being designed in a sequence, i.e. the global shape is designed based on aesthetics, environmental aspects, boundary conditions and other architectural and functional criteria. The structural behavior and efficiency is only considered in the next step (Cruz [10]). The current developed software for the design process of BATH (Lienhard and Knippers [23]) (Van Mele *et al.* [35]) (Piker [30]) (Holden Deleuran *et al.* [14]) (Suzuki and Knippers [33]) needs a better integration of intuitive design and flexibility for the designer followed by a fast integrated accurate process to a greater use of BATH in architecture (including material properties and 6DOF to fully capture the internal stress state).

Membranes and bending-active gridshells are considered as very efficient structures and span large distances, without a need for intermediate supports (Knippers *et al.* [15]). The combination of both

structural elements, BATH, are still small-spanned, pavilion scaled - research based demonstrators. On the one hand the design and simulation of these structures is complex, cf. previous paragraph, on the other hand the construction process is very complex as well. There is a big step between simulating and building a structural demonstrator. The membrane needs to be doubly curved and has to have a reasonable amount of bi-axial prestress, the cutting pattern of the fabric is not stressed within a rigid frame and needs to be designed carefully. The connection between bending-active elements and the membrane considering this prestress is still problematic as well (Slabbinck *et al.* [32]).

It appears that a number of built structures demonstrate the feasibility and their integration into the world of architecture. Current research considers the deployability and adaptability of these structures, using multiple stages of equilibrium. The future for these structures, in the opinion of these authors, is in the field of local BATH structures due to their redundancy and high structural efficiency, additionally there is no limit to multiple stages of equilibrium compared to global BATH where the membrane has to bend the bending-active elements, reducing the possibilities of later form variation.

5. Summary of proposed terminology

System hybrid structures – structures that are global or local bending-active tensile hybrid structures cf. 2.2.

Global BATH structures – structures where the global form is stable self-stressed-equilibrating relying on a system of interdependent bending-active and membrane elements, cf. 2.2.1, e.g. Marrakech Umbrella (Lienhard and Knippers [20]).

Local BATH structures – structures where the global form is stable self-equilibrating or self-stressed-equilibrating, the local bending stresses of the bending-active elements is resolved different from the membrane, but still relying on a system of interdependent bending-active and membrane elements, cf. 2.2.2, e.g. Textile Hybrid M1 (Ahlquist *et al.* [3]).

BAT structures – structures where the bending-active and membrane elements have no interdependent relation, cf. 2.2.3, e.g. Bending-active canopy (De Laet *et al.* [11]).

Stable self-equilibrated structures – structures that can reestablish its equilibrium after an impact of external loads, and all forces are resolved through a form-finding process, cf. 3, e.g. Restrained arch (Alpermann and Gengnagel [4]).

Stable self-stressed-equilibrated structures – structures that can reestablish its equilibrium after an impact of external loads, and requires no external support to maintain its non-externally-loaded form and internally-introduced stresses created through bending are handled by the self-tensioning, cf. 3, e.g. BAT wing (Off [27]).

6. Conclusion

There has been a confusion in terminology describing BATH structures built to date, the aim of this paper is to resolve this through the presented terms, i.e. global BATH structures, local BATH structures, BAT structures, self-equilibrated structures and self-stressed-equilibrated structures. Defining these terms are important as BATH structures are demonstrated to be feasible and integrated into the world of architecture, and pushed for continued development due to their advantages, specifically in the case of stable self-stressed-equilibrated local BATH structures.

7. Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 642877. Special thanks to James Solly.

References

- [1] Adriaenssens S., Stressed spline structures. PhD diss., University of Bath, Bath, 2000.
- [2] Adriaenssens S., Feasibility Study of Medium Span Spliced Spline Stressed Membranes. *International Journal of Space Structures*, 2008; **23** (4); 243-251.
- [3] Ahlquist S., Menges A., Lienhard J. and Knippers J., Textile hybrid M1 at La Tour de l'Architecte- Research on Hybrid Form-and Bending Systems. *TensiNews, newsletter of the European Based network for the Design and Realisation of Tensile Structures*, 2013; **5**; 6-9.
- [4] Alpermann H. and Gengnagel C., Shaping actively-bent elements by restraining systems. *Conference proceedings IASS-APCS symposium: From Spatial Structures to Space Structures*, 2012.
- [5] Alpermann H., Gengnagel C., Restraining actively-bent structures by membranes. *International Conference on Textile Composites and Inflatable Structures: Structural membranes*, Eds. Bletzinger K.-U., Kröplin B. and Onate E., 2013.
- [6] Belenya E., Prestressed load-bearing metal structures, *MIR publishers*, 1977.
- [7] Beukers A. and van Hinte E., *Lightness: The inevitable renaissance of minimum energy structures*. (4th ed.), 010 Publishers, Rotterdam, 2005.
- [8] Brancart S., De Laet L., Vergauwen A. and Temmerman N., Transformable active bending: a kinematical concept, *WIT Transactions on The Built Environment*, 2014; **136**.
- [9] Correia de Melo J. V., Ripper J. L. M. and Moreira L. E., Development of bamboo structures based on minimal surfaces and natural formations. *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium: Beyond the limit of man*, 2013.
- [10] Cruz P. J. S., Structures and Architecture. Beyond their Limits. *CRC Press*, 2016.
- [11] De Laet L., Slabbinck E., Van Mele T. and Block P., Case study: a modular, self-tensioned, bending-active canopy. *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium: Beyond the limit of man*, 2013.
- [12] Engel H., Tragsysteme, Structure Systems. *Ostfilern: Hatje Cantz*, 2009.
- [13] Gioncu V., Keeping pace with progress: from reinforced concrete shells to membrane structures. *Space Structures*. Eds. Parke G. and Disney P., 2002; **5**; 77-86.
- [14] Holden Deleuran A., Schmeck M., Quinn G., Gengnagel C., Tamke M. and Ramsgaard Thomsen M., The Tower: Modelling, Analysis and Construction of Bending Active Tensile Membrane Hybrid Structures. *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium: Future Visions*, 2015.
- [15] Knippers J., Cremers J., Gabler M. and Lienhard J., *Construction manual for polymers + membranes: materials, semi-finished products, form-finding design*. Birkhauser Architecture, Basel, 2011.
- [16] Kooi B.W. and Berman C.A., An Approach to the Study of Ancient Archery using Mathematical Modelling. *Antiquity*, 1997; **71** (271); 124-134.
- [17] Kotelnikova-Weiler N., Douthe C., Lafuente Hernandez E., Baverel O., Gengnagel C. and Caron J.-F., Materials for Actively-Bent Structures. *Journal of Space Structures*, 2013; **28** (3&4); 229-240.
- [18] Krasko J., Daten und Fakten der Multihalle, Factsheet of the Stadt Mannheim, www.akbw.de/uploads/user_upload/Factsheet_Multihalle.pdf [online], 2016.
- [19] Lienhard J., Schleicher S. and Knippers J., Bending-active Structures – Research Pavilion ICD/ITKE, *Proceedings of the International Symposium of the IABSE-IASS*, 2011.
- [20] Lienhard J. and Knippers J., Permanent and convertible membrane structures with intricate bending-active support system. *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium*, 2012.

- [21] Lienhard J., Ahlquist S., Knippers J. and Menges A., Extending the Functional and Formal vocabulary of tensile membrane structures through the interaction with bending-active elements. *Proceedings of the TensiNet Symposium [RE]Thinking Lightweight Structures*, eds. Bongers-Balz H., Mollaert M. and Pusa E., 2013, 109-118.
- [22] Lienhard J., Alpermann H., Gengnagel C. and Knippers J., Active Bending, a Review on structures where bending is used as a self formation process. *International Journal of Space Structures*, 2013; **28**; 187-196.
- [23] Lienhard J. and Knippers J., Bending-Active Textile Hybrids, *Journal of the International Association for Shell and Spatial Structures*, 2015; **56** (1); 37-48.
- [24] Luchsinger H. R. and Crettol C., Synergetic structures and Tensairity ®. *Engineering Structures*, 2007; 207-216.
- [25] Mann, A.P., Design and Fabrication of the new Wembley Stadium Roof, presented on November 16, 2006, www.mae.uk.com/Wembley%20Stadium%20with%20Pictures.PDF [online].
- [26] Muttoni A., *The Art of Structures*. EPFL Press, 1 Edition, Lausanne, 2011.
- [27] Off R., New trends on membrane and shell structures- Examples of bat-sail and cushion-belt technologies. *International Conference on Structures*, eds. Cruz P.J.S., 2010, 25-28.
- [28] Oxford dictionary, © 2017 Oxford University Press, en.oxforddictionaries.com [online], 2017.
- [29] Philipp B. and Bletzinger K.-U., Hybrid structures- Enlarging the design space of architectural membranes, *Journal of the IASS*, 2013; **54** (4); 281-291.
- [30] Piker D., Kangaroo: Form Finding with Computational Physics. *Architectural Design*, 2013; **83** (2); 136-137.
- [31] Quinn G., Holden Deleuran A., Piker d., Brandt-Olsen C., Tamke M., Ramsgaard Thomsen M. and Gengnagel C., Calibrated and Interactive Modelling of Form-Active Hybrid Structures, *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium: Spatial Structures in the 21st Century*, 2016.
- [32] Slabbinck E., Körner A. and Knippers J. Torsion as a design driver in plate-bending-active tensile structures. Submitted for *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium: Interfaces: Architecture, Engineering, science*, Hamburg, 2017.
- [33] Suzuki S. and Knippers J., Topology-driven form-finding: Implementation of an Evolving Network Model for Extending Design Spaces in Dynamic Relaxation, *Proceedings of CAADRIA: Protocols, flows and glitches*, Eds. Raonic A., Herr C., Wash G. *et al.*, China, 2017.
- [34] Vambersky J.N.J.A., High-Rise Buildings in the Netherlands: Hybrid Structures and Precast Concrete. *CTBUH 2004 Seoul Conference*, 2004; 136-143.
- [35] Van Mele T., De Laet L., Veenendaal D., Mollaert M., Block P., Shaping tension structures by actively bent linear elements. *Journal of Space Structures*, 2013; **28** (3&4); 127-135.
- [36] Vineetha N.R., Menon A. and Gettu R., Seismic Response of Hybrid Buildings. *15 WCEE Lisboa*, 2012.